

Supplementary Figure S1: Collagen peptide mass fingerprint (top) for *Salmo salar* which visualises both isoforms of various peptides from each amino acid α -chain (insets, bottom). Blue letters denote the region of the spectrum in focus. Peptide codes in green relate to the α -chain and peptide position.

